

Polymerization of acrylonitrile initiated by the vanadium(v)-potassium thiocyanate redox system : a kinetic study

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Polymerization of acrylonitrile, initiated by the free radicals formed *in situ* in the vanadium(v)-thiocyanate redox system has been studied in aqueous sulfuric acid and perchloric acid media in the temperature range 28–38°. The rate of polymerization (R_p) and the rate of vanadium(v) disappearance have been measured. The effects of some water-miscible organic solvents, surfactants and complexing agents on the rate of polymerization are investigated. The temperature dependence of the rate has been studied and the activation parameters are computed. A mechanism consistent with the experimental data is suggested.

Redox polymerization of vinyl monomers initiated by transition metal ions in their higher oxidation states in an aqueous medium can provide valuable information regarding the mechanistic details of the elementary steps¹. Vanadium(v) in acid solution was found to be a powerful oxidant for both organic and inorganic compounds². It was found that vanadium(v) in presence of certain reducing agents initiates vinyl polymerization³. The anomalous kinetic behavior associated with acrylonitrile⁴ polymerization in aqueous medium and the importance of polyacrylonitrile in the fiber industry, have stimulated the choice of this study.

Results and Discussion

From a qualitative perspective it was noted that vanadium(v) or potassium thiocyanate alone do not initiate polymerization under the experimental conditions. When the reaction mixture was treated with benzoquinone, no polymerization occurred. Thus, it was evident that the polymerization was initiated by free radicals generated *in situ* by the reaction between vanadium(v) and potassium thiocyanate. The steady state was reached within 30 min.

Effect of vanadium(v) concentration on the rate : The rate of polymerization increases with an increase in $[V^V]$ in the range 0.005–0.02 mol dm⁻³. This was due to an increase in the concentration of the active species. The order of the reaction was found to be half from the plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [V^V]$ (Fig. 1). The molecular weight (M_v) of the poly-

Fig. 1. (a) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [V^V]$; $[V^V] = 0.005, 0.01, 0.015$ and 0.02 mol dm⁻³, $[NCS^-] = 0.10$ mol dm⁻³, $[AN] = 0.3034$ mol dm⁻³, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³, $[V^{IV}] = 0.02$ mol dm⁻³, $I = 3.0$ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 301 K. (b) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [NCS^-]$; $[V^V] = 0.005$ mol dm⁻³, $[NCS^-] = 0.06, 0.08, 0.10$ and 0.12 mol dm⁻³, $[AN] = 0.3034$ mol dm⁻³, $I = 3.0$ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 301 K.

mer also decreases with increase in concentration of V^V . The rate of vanadium(v) disappearance ($-R_v$) was found to be independent of acrylonitrile concentration but dependent on the concentration of vanadium(v). The rate of vanadium(v) disappearance was found to be first order with respect to vanadium(v).

Effect of thiocyanate ion concentration : The initial rate as well as the maximum conversion increase linearly with the increase in thiocyanate concentration in the range 0.06–0.12 mol dm⁻³. At higher thiocyanate concentration, the rate decreases due to the local over-concentration of free radicals⁵. The order of the reaction with respect to thiocyanate ion concentration was found to be one (Fig. 1b).

Effect of H⁺ ion concentration : The rate of polymerization increases with an increase in [H⁺] in the range 0.1–0.4 mol dm⁻³. At higher [H⁺], there is a decrease in the rate of polymerization, which may be due to a higher rate of oxidation in comparison with the rate of polymerization (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [M]$; $[V^V] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NCS}^-] = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AN}] = 0.3034, 0.4550, 0.7585, 0.9111 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[V^{IV}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $l = 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 301 K. (b) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [H^+]$; $[V^V] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 \text{ and } 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[V^{IV}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $l = 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 301 K.

Effect of monomer concentration : The rate of polymerization increases with increase in monomer concentration in the range 0.3034–0.9102 mol dm⁻³. The order of the reaction with respect to the concentration was found to be 1.1 (Fig. 2a).

Effect of vanadium(IV) concentration : The rate of polymerization decreases with increase in $[V^{IV}]$ in the range 0.01–0.025 mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 3b).

Effect of ionic strength : The rate of polymerization increases with increase in ionic strength by adding sodium perchlorate. This may be due to the salt catalyzing the propagation step via formation of a complex with acrylonitrile⁶.

Effect of water miscible organic solvents : Water miscible organic solvents, such as methanol, ethanol and DMF

were found to depress the rate. These solvents decrease the area of shielding of the strong hydration layer of aqueous medium, resulting in the termination of the radical end of the growing chains⁷.

Fig. 3. (a) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $1/T$; $[V^V] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NCS}^-] = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AN}] = 0.3034 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[V^{IV}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 301, 303, 308, 313 K. (b) Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [V^{IV}]$; $[V^V] = 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NCS}^-] = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AN}] = 0.3034 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[V^{IV}] = 0.01, 0.015, 0.02 \text{ and } 0.025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Effect of temperature : The rate of polymerization increases with increase in temperature (Fig. 3a). The energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters calculated are : $E_a^* = 45.26 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^* = 42.75 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^* = -140.0 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$,

$\Delta G^* = 84.90 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in sulfuric acid medium; and

$E_a^* = 30.06 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^* = 27.56 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^* = -184.88 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$,

$\Delta G^* = 83.21 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in perchloric acid medium.

Mechanism and rate law : From the proportionality obtained between the measurable parameters and the variables, the following reaction scheme is suggested, involving initiation by the free radicals produced by the interaction of vanadium(v) with thiocyanate and the termination by mutual interaction of the growing radicals.

(i) Primary radical production :

In the presence of the acrylonitrile monomer, the free radical R* starts the chain reaction as shown below :

(ii) Initiation :

(iii) Propagation :

(iv) Termination :

The formation of $V(OH)_2(SCN)_2^+$ involves the fast equilibria (1-4). In the presence of the radical scavenger acrylonitrile, step (6) is insignificant and the rate of vanadium(V) disappearance is given by the forward step of reaction (5),

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = k_5 [V(OH)_2(SCN)_2^+] \quad (11)$$

$$= K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 k_5 [VO_2^+] [H^+]^2 [SCN^-]^2 \quad (12)$$

Taking into account the above reaction scheme and applying steady state assumption to both $[R^*]$ and $[RM_n^*]$ separately, the following expression is possible and derivable for the rate of polymerization.

$$\frac{d[R^*]}{dt} = k_5 [V(OH)_2(SCN)_2^+] - k_{-5}[R^*][VO_2SCN^+] - k_6[R^*] - k_1[R^*][M] \quad (13)$$

$$[R^*] = \frac{k_5 [V(OH)_2(SCN)_2^+]}{k_{-5}[VO_2SCN^+] + k_6 + k_1[M]} \quad (14)$$

Substituting for $k_5 [V(OH)_2(SCN)_2^+]$ we get,

$$[R^*] = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 k_5 [VO_2^+] [H^+]^2 [SCN^-]^2}{k_{-5}[VO_2SCN^+] + k_6 + k_1[M]} \quad (15)$$

Since propagation is the stage that involves the major consumption of the monomer, the rate of monomer loss can be expressed in terms of propagation only,

$$R_p = -d[M]/dt = k_p [RM_n^*] [M] \quad (16)$$

Based on the usual assumption that the radical reactivity is independent of the radical chain-length, the rate of polymerization is given by

$$R_p = k_p [RM_n^*] [M] \quad (17)$$

In the overall polymerization, the rate of initiation and the rate of termination become equal, resulting in a steady concentration of free radicals.

$$k_1[R^*][M] = k_t [RM_n^*]^2, \text{ where } RM_n^* \approx RM_m^*$$

$$[RM_n^*] = \left(\frac{k_1}{k_t} \right)^{1/2} [R^*]^{1/2} [M]^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

The rate of polymerization, R_p is given by

$$R_p = k_p [M] [RM_n^*] \quad (19)$$

$$[R_p] = k_p \left(\frac{k_1}{k_t} \right)^{1/2} [R^*]^{1/2} [M]^{3/2} \quad (20)$$

Substituting for $[R^*]$,

$$R_p = k_p \left[\frac{k_1}{k_t} K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 K_5 \right]^{1/2} \frac{[M]^{3/2} [VO_2^+]^{1/2} [H^+] [SCN^-]}{\{k_{-5}[VO_2SCN^+] + k_6 + k_1[M]\}^{1/2}}$$

The dependence of R_p on $[M]^{1.5}$, $[V^V]^{1/2}$, $[H^+]$, $[SCN^-]$ and $[V^{IV}]^{-1/2}$ all of them are observed and favour the above scheme.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile was freed from the inhibitor⁸ by treating with alkali, washed with orthophosphoric acid and distilled water, dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$, and finally distilled under reduced pressure in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The middle fraction of the second distillate was collected and stored at 5°. Sodium metavanadate, potassium thiocyanate, sodium perchlorate, sodium bisulfate, sulfuric acid, perchloric acid and vanadyl sulfate were of A.R. grade. Water dis-

titled twice over alkaline permanganate, was used to prepare all solutions. Oxygen-free nitrogen was used.

The standard solution of vanadium(v) was prepared by suspending sodium metavanadate in distilled water and adding 10 M perchloric acid, and its concentration was determined. The acidity in the vanadium(v) stock solution was determined potentiometrically. Vanadyl perchlorate solution was prepared by the addition of stoichiometrically equivalent of BaClO₄ to vanadyl sulfate solution and filtering off the barium sulfate formed.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction vessels used for the experiments were pyrex glass vessels fitted with B24 sockets and cone fitted with inlet and outlet tubes for nitrogen. The system consisting of KNCS, H₂SO₄ or HClO₄, acrylonitrile, V^{IV}, NaClO₄ (for ionic strength adjustment) and water (to keep the total volume constant) was thermostated at the desired temperature and de-aerated by passing oxygen-free nitrogen for 20–30 min, followed by the addition of de-aerated vanadium(v) solution. A wash bottle containing an aqueous solution of acrylonitrile, whose concentration was the same as in the reaction vessel was interposed between the nitrogen train and the reaction vessel to avoid any loss of monomer due to deaeration. Polymerization started without any induction period as indicated by the appearance of turbidity. At an appropriate time interval, the reaction was arrested by freezing the reaction mixture by adding ice-cold water and blowing air in. The polyacrylonitrile was filtered from the reaction mixture, washed with distilled water and dried at 70°. The rate of polymerization was calculated from the initial slope of percentage conversion versus time plot.

The filtrate was treated with a mixture containing excess of standard Fe^{II} solution, phosphoric acid and mercuric chloride. The unreacted Fe^{II} was titrated with standard vanadium solution using barium diphenylamine sulfonate

as redox indicator and the rate of vanadium (v) was determined.

The molecular weight (M_v) of polyacrylonitrile was determined by viscosity measurements using an Ubbelohde suspended level dilution viscometer. The intrinsic viscosity (η) for the polymer solution were determined, and M_v evaluated, (η) = $(3.335 \times 10^{-4}) M_v^{0.72}$ for polyacrylonitrile in DMF at 30°.

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